

Spam E-Mail Detection Using Gradient Boosting Ensemble Learning Algorithms

Bindeshwar S. Kushwaha

bindeshwar.kush@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7335-9722>¹ and

Pramod K. Mishra

pkmisra@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0667-1563>²

^{1,2}Department of Computer Science, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi, India

Abstract

Email communication is a very popular means of interaction in organizations such as schools and companies. However, not all emails are legitimate, many are marketing-oriented or phishing attempts, commonly referred to as spam. Manually filtering spam emails is not feasible and can be a tedious task. In this paper, we develop a machine learning model to classify emails as either spam or legitimate. We use boosting techniques, namely AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, XGBoost, LightGBM (LGBM), and CatBoost, which are types of ensemble learning methods that have shown promising results in various domains. We evaluate these models using performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score across different learning rates and numbers of estimators. Additionally, we conduct a statistical significance test using the 5x2cv paired t-test to determine whether the observed differences in performance are statistically meaningful. Our findings indicate that LGBM and CatBoost demonstrate similar and superior performance compared to the other algorithms. AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting exhibit similar but relatively poorer performance. XGBoost performs better than AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting but falls short of LGBM and CatBoost.

1 Introduction

Since any user with an email address can send messages to other users without restriction or control, spam has become a growing concern. While it's possible to block specific email addresses, this approach is not practical when hundreds of spam emails arrive in a single inbox daily. Over time, the misuse of email communication has increased significantly. Many emails appear to be legitimate but are actually harmful. If a user clicks on a malicious link contained in such an email, it may lead to the theft

of sensitive information, such as credit card details or personal data or result in the installation of malicious software on the user's system. These types of spam emails are known as phishing emails [1], and they can cause harm in multiple ways. Phishing attacks are designed to extract user information, thereby compromising both privacy and security. Email marketing is one of the most cost-effective forms of promotion, where digital marketing companies use automation software to send emails at predefined intervals [2]. However, these systems sometimes send repeated emails under the guise of reminders, which can become annoying for users. Email communication is widely adopted due to its low cost and rapid transmission compared to other modes of communication. However, this convenience has also made it an attractive medium for spammers to disseminate unsolicited advertisements and malicious content. The overwhelming volume of spam emails often makes it difficult for users to identify legitimate messages.

Spam emails not only waste users' time but also consume network bandwidth and may lead to financial fraud by luring users into phishing schemes. Additionally, they occupy server storage, consume computational resources, and contribute to unnecessary network traffic. According to a report by Kaspersky Lab, 45.56% of all emails in 2021 were classified as spam, with malware, particularly Trojans being the most common type of malicious attachment [3]. The volume of spam emails continues to increase daily, posing ongoing challenges to email security and user privacy. Manually filtering spam emails from legitimate ones is not feasible and can be a cumbersome task. Therefore, there is a need for automated mechanisms capable of distinguishing between spam and legitimate emails efficiently and accurately. Over the years, several approaches have been developed to combat spam. Early techniques relied on rule-based systems [4, 5], which filtered emails based on specific keywords. However, such systems were limited in adaptability and failed to detect spam when even minor modifications were made to the content. In contrast, machine learning approaches [6, 7, 8] have gained popularity among researchers and practitioners. These methods leverage data-driven models that learn patterns from datasets, enabling them to adapt to evolving definitions of spam.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a review of related work; Section 3 describes the boosting algorithms used; Section 4 introduces the dataset; Sections 5 and 6 provide performance evaluation of the machine learning models. Section 7 presents a comparative analysis using statistical significance testing, and finally, Section 8 concludes the paper and outlines future directions.

2 Related Work

A considerable amount of research has been conducted in the domain of spam detection using machine learning algorithms. In [9], the authors employ Naïve Bayes (NB), Neural Networks (NN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Relevance Vector Machines (RVM) to develop spam filters, evaluating the models based on precision and recall while varying the feature set size. Similarly, [10] constructs an ensemble model comprising SVM, Decision Tree, and Neural Network, and evaluates its performance using accuracy as the primary metric. In addition to conventional algorithms such as Naïve

Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and SVM, [7] explores a rule-based machine learning approach by applying Artificial Immune System (AIS) algorithms for spam classification. The models are assessed using precision, recall, and accuracy. Furthermore, when the input data consists of textual content, Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques can be employed for feature extraction, thereby enabling the construction of more effective and context-aware classification models. However, when spam content is embedded in images, deep learning-based models become essential. In [11], a model is proposed using Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) to detect email spam containing images. The model is evaluated using F1-score and accuracy metrics. Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) is a pre-trained deep learning model designed for Natural Language Processing tasks [12]. In [13], the authors utilize the BERT model to develop a spam detection system, which is evaluated using accuracy and F1-score. In addition, [14] presents a hybrid spam detection model capable of identifying both textual and image-based spam. The proposed system integrates Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for text-based spam detection and CNNs for image-based spam classification. The model's performance is evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score metrics.

3 Ensemble Learning Techniques

Ensemble methods are powerful and widely adopted classification techniques that aggregate the predictions of multiple weak learners to construct a more accurate and robust model. A weak learner refers to a model that performs only marginally better than random guessing. However, when multiple weak learners are strategically combined, the resulting ensemble can achieve significantly improved predictive performance compared to any single constituent model.

In addition to enhancing accuracy, ensemble learning also plays a critical role in mitigating over fitting by reducing variance and improving the model's ability to generalize to unseen data. Among the various ensemble strategies proposed in the literature, bagging and boosting have emerged as the most prominent and extensively utilized approaches.

3.1 Bagging Algorithms

The fundamental principle of Bagging (Bootstrap Aggregating) [15] lies in generating multiple bootstrap samples by randomly drawing instances from the original dataset with replacement. For each of these samples, an independent base learner is trained, and the ensemble prediction is obtained by aggregating the outputs commonly through averaging for regression tasks or majority voting for classification tasks. This parallel ensemble methodology significantly reduces model variance and enhances generalization performance by mitigating the risk of overfitting to the training data. Owing to its robustness and simplicity, Bagging has demonstrated efficacy across a wide range of supervised learning problems, including both regression and classification tasks.

3.2 Boosting Algorithms

Boosting is an ensemble learning technique that combines multiple weak learners in a sequential manner, where each subsequent model is trained to correct the errors made by its predecessor. The misclassifications or residuals computed as the difference between the actual (labeled) and predicted values guide the learning process of subsequent models. Unlike parallel ensemble methods such as Bagging, Boosting focuses on progressively improving performance by emphasizing instances that are difficult to predict. This sequential correction mechanism enables Boosting to effectively reduce both bias and variance, thereby addressing issues related to underfitting and overfitting. Prominent Boosting algorithms include Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost), Gradient Boosting (GB), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM), and Categorical Boosting (CatBoost).

3.2.1 Adaptive Boosting

Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost) [16] is an iterative ensemble learning algorithm that aims to improve classification performance by sequentially training a series of weak learners, typically *decision stumps*—i.e., shallow decision trees with a single split (one root and two leaves). Initially, each training instance is assigned an equal weight of $\frac{1}{n}$, where n is the total number of samples. In each iteration, a decision stump is constructed using the feature that minimizes the *Gini index*, thereby selecting the most discriminative feature at that step.

The weak learner $h_t(x)$ is then used to classify the training instances, and the *weighted classification error* ε_t at iteration t is computed as:

$$\varepsilon_t = \sum_{i=1}^n D_t(i) \cdot \mathbb{I}[h_t(x_i) \neq y_i] \quad (1)$$

where $D_t(i)$ denotes the weight of instance i at iteration t , and $\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$ is the indicator function that equals 1 if the condition is true and 0 otherwise.

Subsequently, the contribution (or say) of the weak learner $h_t(x)$ in the final ensemble is quantified using the coefficient α_t , defined as:

$$\alpha_t = \frac{1}{2} \log \left(\frac{1 - \varepsilon_t}{\varepsilon_t} \right) \quad (2)$$

This coefficient increases for classifiers with lower error rates, thereby assigning more influence to accurate learners.

The weights of the training instances are then updated to emphasize the misclassified examples. Specifically, the updated weights $D_{t+1}(i)$ are computed as:

$$D_{t+1}(i) = \begin{cases} D_t(i) \cdot e^{-\alpha_t}, & \text{if } h_t(x_i) = y_i \\ D_t(i) \cdot e^{\alpha_t}, & \text{if } h_t(x_i) \neq y_i \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

To ensure that $D_{t+1}(i)$ forms a valid probability distribution, the weights are *normalized* such that $\sum_{i=1}^n D_{t+1}(i) = 1$. This reweighting mechanism ensures that subsequent weak learners focus more on the hard-to-classify instances.

Finally, a new dataset is generated from the original training set based on the updated weights, with higher probability of selecting misclassified instances. This process is repeated for a predefined number of iterations or until convergence.

3.2.2 Gradient Boosting for Classification

As the name indicates gradient boost algorithm [17] is a boosting algorithm with a gradient descent optimization algorithm [18] for minimizing a loss function. A loss function determines how well a model performs. In addition, the algorithm can be used for regression as well as for classification. The algorithm finds a model $F^*(x)$ on training dataset $\{x_i, y_i\}_{i=1}^n$ after minimizing a loss function. First of all, the model is initialized by a constant value

$$F_0(x) = \arg \min_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \gamma) \quad (4)$$

Where $F_0(x)$ is the initial model, L is a differentiable loss function. For binary classification, the algorithm uses binary cross-entropy cost function which is,

$$y \log(\text{odds}) + \log(1 + e^{\text{odds}}) \quad (5)$$

Where $\text{odds} = \frac{p}{1-p}$, where p is the probability of occurrence of class 1 and $1 - p$ is the probability of occurrence of class 2.

Thereafter, it computes

$$r_{im} = - \left[\frac{\partial L(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)} \right]_{F(x)=F_{m-1}(x)} \quad (6)$$

Where m is the iteration number and i is i^{th} instance. Then algorithm trains weak learners using the new dataset $\{(x_i, r_{im})\}_{i=1}^n$. Then it computes the value of γ_m using

$$\gamma_m = \arg \min_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, F_{m-1}(x_i) + \gamma h_m(x_i)) \quad (7)$$

After computing γ_m , the algorithm updates the model

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \gamma_m h_m(x) \quad (8)$$

After M iterations, algorithm produces the final model as $F_M(x)$. Decision trees are prone to over-fit training data due to high variance; to control variance, gradient boosting machine uses parameter ν which reduces the number of trees that prevents over fitting of training data, and helps to generalize the model.

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \nu \gamma_m h_m(x) \quad (9)$$

3.3 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

Extreme Gradient Boosting, or **XGBoost**, is an advanced implementation of the gradient boosting framework that incorporates regularization to enhance model generalization and mitigate over fitting [19]. The algorithm optimizes an objective function that comprises two components: a differentiable convex loss function $l(\hat{y}_i, y_i)$ measuring the difference between the predicted and actual values, and a regularization term $\Omega(f_k)$ that penalizes model complexity.

$$L(\phi) = \sum_i l(\hat{y}_i, y_i) + \sum_k \Omega(f_k) \quad (10)$$

The regularization term $\Omega(f_k)$ is defined as:

$$\Omega(f) = \gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \|w\|^2 \quad (11)$$

Here, T denotes the number of leaves in the tree, w represents the vector of scores on each leaf, and λ and γ are hyperparameters that control the regularization strength. Specifically, λ imposes L_2 -regularization on the leaf weights to reduce model complexity, while γ is used to control tree pruning by setting a minimum loss reduction threshold required to make a further partition.

If the regularization term $\Omega(f_k)$ is omitted, XGBoost reduces to the traditional gradient boosting algorithm. In addition to regularization, XGBoost employs several optimization techniques such as sparsity-aware splitting, weighted quantile sketch for approximate tree learning, and a gain-based scoring mechanism to determine the best split, resulting in an efficient and scalable framework for structured data learning.

3.2.4. Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)

Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) [20] is an efficient and scalable implementation of the Gradient Boosting framework designed for high-performance learning on large datasets. Unlike traditional Gradient Boosting algorithms that compute information gain using all training samples leading to high computational cost, LightGBM introduces two key innovations to optimize performance: Gradient-based One-Side Sampling (GOSS) and Exclusive Feature Bundling (EFB). The GOSS technique leverages the observation that instances with larger gradients contribute more to the information gain during tree construction. Therefore, LightGBM selectively retains instances with large gradients and randomly samples from those with small gradients. This focused sampling reduces the number of data points used in split finding without significantly compromising accuracy, resulting in substantial computational efficiency. In addition, LightGBM employs EFB, a dimensionality reduction technique that combines mutually exclusive features i.e., features that rarely take non-zero values simultaneously into a single bundled feature. This bundling reduces the number of effective features without incurring significant information loss, further improving training speed and memory efficiency. By integrating GOSS and EFB, LightGBM achieves both faster training and higher scalability while maintaining competitive predictive performance, particularly in scenarios involving high-dimensional and large-scale structured data.

3.2.5. Categorical Boosting Algorithm (CatBoost)

Categorical Boosting, commonly known as **CatBoost** [21], is a sophisticated implementation of the Gradient Boosting framework, specifically designed to handle categorical features efficiently and accurately. One of the key distinguishing features of CatBoost is its ability to process categorical variables during training, eliminating the need for extensive pre-processing techniques such as one-hot or label encoding.

CatBoost employs an innovative technique based on target statistics and ordered boosting to transform categorical features in a way that reduces over fitting and information leakage. While the algorithm is optimized for datasets with categorical variables, it is also capable of handling numerical features; however, in practice, its performance advantage is most prominent in scenarios with a significant number of categorical attributes.

By natively incorporating categorical feature handling and employing ordered boosting to eliminate prediction shift, CatBoost achieves competitive accuracy and robustness across a wide range of supervised learning tasks, particularly in domains such as e-commerce, recommendation systems, and tabular data analytics.

4. Data Set Description and Spam Detection Model

We utilized the Spambase dataset, publicly available from the UCI Machine Learning Repository [22], which comprises 57 features and 4601 instances. The final attribute in the dataset serves as the binary target variable, where a value of 0 denotes a non-spam (ham) email, and 1 indicates a spam email. This dataset is widely recognized and openly accessible for benchmarking and research in spam email classification tasks

5. Performance Evaluation

For the performance evaluation of the proposed models, we considered a set of widely used evaluation metrics that provide a comprehensive assessment of classification effectiveness [23, 24]. These metrics offer insights into the predictive capability and generalization performance of the model. To systematically analyze model behavior, we varied two key hyperparameters: the learning rate and the number of estimators.

Evaluation Metrics

Precision is defined as:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (10)$$

Where TP is True Positive and FP is False Positive. Precision measures the relevance of the positive predictions made by the model. It is the ratio of accurate positive

Figure 1: Spam classification using a machine learning model trained on the UCI dataset.

Table 1: Parameters for Experiments and Their Values

Parameter(s)	Value(s)
Frameworks	scikit-learn, mlxtend
Algorithms	AdaBoost, Gradient Boost, XGBoost, CatBoost and LGBM
Number of Estimators	1 to 100
Learning Rate	0.03 to 0.30
Performance Metrics	Precision, Recall, F1-Measure and Accuracy

predictions to the total number of positive predictions. Precision values range from 0 to 1.

Recall is defined as:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (11)$$

Where FN is False Negative. Recall measures the ability of the model to identify all relevant instances. It is the ratio of correct positive predictions to the total number of actual positive instances. Recall values also range from 0 to 1.

F1-Score is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, and it provides a balanced measure of a model's performance, especially when there is an imbalance between Precision and Recall. The F1-Score is defined as:

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (12)$$

The F1-Score also lies between 0 and 1.

Accuracy is defined as the ratio of correctly classified examples to all classified examples:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (13)$$

Where TN is True Negative, and FP is False Positive. Accuracy provides an overall measure of model performance and, like the other metrics, ranges from 0 to 1.

For model evaluation, we utilize the library [25], which is widely used by both researchers and developers for building machine learning models and performing evaluations. We also rely on the library [26] to compute the bias and variance of the model's errors.

In our performance analysis, we focus on two parameters: the number of estimators and the learning rate, which play crucial roles in the performance of ensemble models.

5.1. Number of Estimators versus Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and Accuracy

In ensemble learning, the number of estimators refers to the number of weak learners used in the model, and in this study, we increment the number of estimators from 1 to 100. The performance of different ensemble models in terms of precision, as shown in Fig. 2, varies as the number of estimators increases.

Figure 2: Number of Estimators versus Precision.

From Figure 2, it is evident that the precision of models like CatBoost, Adaptive Boosting, and Light Gradient Boosting fluctuates as the number of estimators increases. On the other hand, both Gradient Boosting and Extreme Gradient Boosting maintain relatively stable precision values throughout the range of estimators. This observation suggests that while some models show variability with the number of estimators, others demonstrate more consistent performance.

Figure 3: Number of Estimators versus Recall.

As shown in Fig. 3, Light Gradient Boosting consistently achieves the highest recall across different numbers of estimators, outperforming all other ensemble algorithms. It is followed by Extreme Gradient Boosting and Categorical Boosting, which also exhibit strong recall performance. In contrast, Adaptive Boosting and traditional Gradient Boosting demonstrate comparatively lower recall values. A noteworthy observation from the plot is that after approximately 40 estimators, the recall values for all algorithms tend to stabilize, indicating diminishing gains in recall with the addition of more estimators beyond this point.

Figure 4: Number of Estimators versus F1-Score.

Fig. 4 presents the variation in F1-score with respect to the number of estimators. The F1-score, being the harmonic mean of precision and recall, provides a balanced measure of model accuracy. Among the evaluated algorithms, Light Gradient Boosting and Extreme Gradient Boosting exhibit superior performance across most estimator counts, followed closely by Categorical Boosting. In comparison, Adaptive Boosting and traditional Gradient Boosting achieve lower F1-scores. Similar to the trend observed in recall (Fig. 3), the performance of all algorithms tends to stabilize after approximately 40 estimators, indicating limited improvements with further increases.

Figure 5: Number of Estimators versus Accuracy.

Fig. 5 illustrates the variation in model accuracy with respect to the number of estimators. Accuracy represents the overall performance of a model and is a key criterion for model selection and deployment. As evident from the figure, Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) consistently demonstrate the highest accuracy among all the algorithms evaluated. These are followed by Categorical Boosting (CatBoost), which performs better than both Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost) and Gradient Boosting. AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting exhibit comparable accuracy levels, albeit lower than LGBM, XGBoost, and CatBoost. Furthermore, similar to the trends observed in recall and F1-score, accuracy tends to plateau after approximately 40 estimators, suggesting that increasing the number of estimators beyond this point yields marginal improvement in overall performance.

5.2. Learning Rate versus Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and Accuracy

Learning rate is a crucial hyperparameter in boosting algorithms, as it determines the contribution of each weak learner during the model's iterative learning process. Its value typically lies between 0 and 1. In this analysis, the learning rate was varied from 0.03 to 0.30 in steps of 0.03, and its impact on precision, recall, F1-score, and accuracy was examined.

Figure 6: Learning Rate versus Precision.

As illustrated in Fig. 6, the precision performance of Gradient Boosting, Extreme Gradient Boosting, Light Gradient Boosting, and Categorical Gradient Boosting remains consistently high across different learning rates. In contrast, Adaptive Boosting shows a clear upward trend but lags behind all other algorithms in terms of precision. Its performance starts significantly lower and gradually improves, yet does not reach the levels attained by the other ensemble methods, indicating its relative inefficiency in handling precision with varying learning rates.

Figure 7: Learning Rate versus Recall.

Fig. 7 presents the relationship between learning rate and recall for various boosting algorithms. Among them, CatBoost and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM) exhibit the highest and most consistent recall performance across the entire range of learning rates. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) also shows strong performance, outperforming both Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost) and traditional Gradient Boosting. Notably, AdaBoost demonstrates the lowest recall values throughout, indicating its relatively poor ability to correctly identify positive cases when the learning rate is varied. These results highlight the robustness of CatBoost and LGBM in maintaining high recall regardless of the learning rate setting.

Figure 8: Learning Rate versus F1-Measure.

Fig. 8 shows the effect of varying the learning rate on the F1-score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM) consistently achieves the highest F1-scores across the learning rate range, indicating its strong balance between precision and recall. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) and CatBoost also perform comparably well, showing only slight variations below LGBM. Gradient Boosting achieves moderate performance, outperforming Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost), which records the lowest F1-scores throughout. These results reaffirm the effectiveness of LGBM, CatBoost, and XGBoost in maintaining robust classification performance under varying learning rates.

Figure 9: Learning Rate versus Accuracy.

Fig. 9 illustrates the variation in accuracy with respect to learning rate for different boosting algorithms. Accuracy, which reflects the overall performance of a model, reveals clear distinctions among the methods. Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM) achieves the highest accuracy, particularly when the learning rate exceeds 0.15. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) and CatBoost also exhibit strong and consistent performance, closely following LGBM. In contrast, Gradient Boosting performs moderately well, while Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost) consistently lags behind all other algorithms. These results emphasize the effectiveness of LGBM, XG-

Boost, and CatBoost in maintaining superior accuracy across a wide range of learning rates.

6. Bias and Variance Error Analysis

In this study, a binary classification task is considered, for which the binary log loss cost function is employed. This loss function is a variant of the 0-1 loss function and is particularly suited for probabilistic classification problems involving two classes. The total error of a learning algorithm can be decomposed into three fundamental components: bias, variance, and irreducible error.

Bias error arises when a model makes strong assumptions about the underlying data distribution, which can lead to systematic errors in predictions. A model with high bias tends to underfit the training data, failing to capture the underlying patterns. In contrast, variance error reflects the sensitivity of a model to fluctuations in the training dataset. Models with high variance typically overfit the training data, capturing noise as if it were signal.

The bias error can be formally defined as:

$$Bias = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y \neq \mathbb{E}[\hat{y}] \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The variance error quantifies the probability that an individual prediction deviates from the expected prediction of the model, and is given by [27]:

$$Variance = P(\hat{y} \neq \mathbb{E}[\hat{y}]) \quad (17)$$

Understanding the trade-off between bias and variance is crucial for selecting an appropriate model and tuning hyperparameters. A good model strikes a balance between underfitting and overfitting to achieve optimal generalization on unseen data.

6.1. Number of Estimators versus Bias and Variance Error

The number of estimators refers to the count of decision trees added sequentially in boosting algorithms. This parameter significantly influences both the bias and variance errors of a model. As the number of estimators increases, the model becomes more complex and capable of capturing intricate patterns in the data. However, it may also increase the risk of overfitting if not regularized properly.

To investigate this effect, we analyzed bias and variance errors separately while varying the number of estimators. Fig. 10 illustrates the relationship between the number of estimators and bias error. It is evident that Gradient Boosting exhibits the

highest bias error across all estimator values, followed by AdaBoost. In contrast, LightGBM, XGBoost, and CatBoost demonstrate significantly lower bias errors, with LightGBM maintaining the lowest bias overall—particularly when the number of estimators exceeds 70.

Figure 10: Number of Estimators versus Bias Error.

Fig. 11 presents the relationship between the number of estimators and variance error. From 1 to 40 estimators, AdaBoost records the highest variance error, followed by CatBoost, LightGBM, and XGBoost, respectively. Interestingly, during this range, Gradient Boosting achieves the lowest variance error. From 40 to 100 estimators, Gradient Boosting continues to exhibit the lowest variance, while AdaBoost consistently retains the highest variance among all models.

Figure 11: Number of Estimators versus Variance Error.

From the analysis, it is evident that XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost outperform Gradient Boosting and AdaBoost in terms of both bias and variance errors. This superior performance is primarily attributed to the advanced regularization techniques embedded in these algorithms, which effectively control both underfitting (bias) and overfitting (variance). These techniques include L1/L2 regularization, leaf-wise tree

growth, and handling categorical features natively—making these algorithms more robust and generalizable.

6.2. Learning Rate versus Bias and Variance Error

The learning rate is a key hyperparameter that controls the contribution of each estimator during the boosting process. It takes values between 0 and 1, and in this study, we varied it from 0.03 to 0.30 to evaluate its impact on bias and variance errors.

Fig. 12 illustrates the relationship between learning rate and bias error. Among the models, AdaBoost consistently exhibits the highest bias across all learning rates, followed by Gradient Boost. In contrast, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LGBM demonstrate lower bias errors, with LGBM achieving the minimum error levels across most of the learning rate spectrum. This suggests that these advanced boosting algorithms are more effective at minimizing bias due to their sophisticated optimization techniques and regularization mechanisms.

Figure 12: Learning Rate versus Bias Error.

Fig. 13 shows how variance error varies with the learning rate. The variance error tends to fluctuate for most algorithms as the learning rate increases, with the exception of AdaBoost, which maintains a relatively stable variance profile. Notably, Gradient Boost starts with the lowest variance error at lower learning rates, but its error increases significantly with higher learning rates. This trend highlights that increasing the learning rate can lead to overfitting, thereby increasing variance.

Figure 13: Learning Rate versus Variance Error.

These observations emphasize that the learning rate not only influences the convergence speed but also significantly affects both bias and variance errors. There exists a trade-off between the number of estimators and the learning rate: when a low number of estimators is used, a higher learning rate may be necessary to maintain performance, and conversely, a lower learning rate may require an increased number of estimators to sufficiently reduce bias and variance. Therefore, careful tuning of both parameters is essential for achieving optimal generalization performance.

7. Statistical Significance Tests for Ensemble Learning Models

In machine learning research, models are commonly compared based on their average performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, or F1-score computed via k -fold cross-validation. While a higher mean performance is typically interpreted as an indicator of a superior model, such conclusions may be affected by sampling variability or statistical chance. To ensure that observed performance differences are meaningful and not merely artifacts of data partitioning, statistical significance tests are essential.

One such widely accepted method is the 5x2 cross-validated paired t -test, originally proposed by [28] and frequently employed in subsequent studies [29, 30]. This method performs two-fold cross-validation, repeated five times, to evaluate the significance of performance differences between two models. In each iteration, the dataset is randomly divided into two equal parts, S_1 and S_2 , each containing 50% of the instances.

For a given replication, model A is trained on S_1 and evaluated on S_2 to produce an error estimate p_A^1 , and vice versa to obtain p_A^2 . Similarly, model B yields error estimates p_B^1 and p_B^2 . The difference in performance for each fold is computed as:

$$p^1 = p_A^1 - p_B^1 \quad (18)$$

$$p^2 = p_A^2 - p_B^2 \quad (19)$$

The variance for the i^{th} replication is given by:

$$s^2 = (p^1 - \bar{p})^2 + (p^2 - \bar{p})^2 \quad (20)$$

where the mean difference \bar{p} is defined as:

$$\bar{p} = \frac{p^1 + p^2}{2}$$

The overall 5x2cv t -statistic is computed as:

$$\tilde{t} = \frac{p_1^1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{5} \sum_{i=1}^5 s_i^2}} \quad (21)$$

This statistic approximately follows a t -distribution with 5 degrees of freedom. Here, s_i^2 denotes the variance from the i^{th} replication, and p_1^1 represents the first performance difference from the first replication.

The hypotheses tested are as follows:

H₀: There is no statistically significant difference between the performances of the two algorithms.

H₁: There is a statistically significant difference between the performances of the two algorithms.

Using the computed t -statistic, a corresponding p -value is derived to evaluate statistical significance. At a 5% significance level (i.e., $\alpha = 0.05$), a p -value greater than 0.05 indicates that the performance difference is not statistically significant and may be attributed to random chance. Conversely, a p -value less than 0.05 suggests that the observed difference is statistically significant and likely reflects a genuine disparity in model performance.

In our study, we applied the 5x2cv paired t -test to evaluate and compare ensemble learning models with 100 estimators across multiple metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. These tests were conducted under a fixed learning rate of 0.30. The results provide insight into whether the observed performance differences among the models are statistically meaningful or simply due to variability in data partitioning.

7.1. Statistical Significance Tests for Number of Estimators vs Performance Parameters

In this section, we report the computed t -statistics and corresponding p -values for various performance metrics across different ensemble models, evaluated at a fixed number of estimators. The statistical significance of the performance differences is assessed using a significance level of 5% (i.e., $\alpha = 0.05$). If the p -value exceeds 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the observed difference in performance is not statistically significant and may have occurred due to random variation. Conversely, a

p -value less than 0.05 leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, suggesting that the performance difference between the models is statistically significant at the 5% level. This analysis helps in validating whether the observed improvements in metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are due to genuine model superiority or can be attributed to chance.

Table 2: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of estimators vs precision.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -2.375$ $p = 0.064$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.666$ $p = 0.045$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -3.910$ $p = 0.011$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.893$ $p = 0.031$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 2.166$ $p = 0.083$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -1.982$ $p = 0.104$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.120$ $p = 0.302$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.372$ $p = 0.178$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 2.666$ $p = 0.045$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.994$ $p = 0.103$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.509$ $p = 0.632$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.015$ $p = 0.988$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 3.910$ $p = 0.011$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.196$ $p = 0.285$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.509$ $p = 0.632$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.452$ $p = 0.670$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 2.893$ $p = 0.031$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.197$ $p = 0.287$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.015$ $p = 0.988$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.452$ $p = 0.670$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

Table 2 presents the p-values assessing whether there is a statistically significant difference in Precision between pairs of algorithms as the number of estimators increases. The results indicate no statistically significant difference in precision between AdaBoost and GradientBoost, suggesting similar performance. However, AdaBoost exhibits a statistically significant difference in precision when compared to XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost. In contrast, GradientBoost does not show any significant precision difference when compared with any of the four algorithms AdaBoost, XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost indicating its consistent performance. Observing the XGBoost row, we find a significant difference in performance only when compared to AdaBoost; it performs similarly to GradientBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost. Finally, LGBM demonstrates significantly different performance in precision compared to AdaBoost and GradientBoost, while it performs comparably to XGBoost and CatBoost.

Table 3: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of estimators vs recall.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -0.511$ $p = 0.631$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.759$ $p = 0.139$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.697$ $p = 0.043$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.950$ $p = 0.050$ $p \approx 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 0.530$ $p = 0.619$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -1.349$ $p = 0.035$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.980$ $p = 0.105$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.125$ $p = 0.301$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 1.759$ $p = 0.139$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.848$ $p = 0.435$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.899$ $p = 0.410$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.018$ $p = 0.918$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 2.697$ $p = 0.043$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.536$ $p = 0.185$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.899$ $p = 0.410$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.771$ $p = 0.476$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 1.950$ $p = 0.050$ $p \approx 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.199$ $p = 0.285$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.018$ $p = 0.918$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.771$ $p = 0.476$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

Table 3 presents the p-values for pairwise comparisons of recall between algorithms, evaluating whether the observed differences are statistically significant at the 5% significance level (i.e., $p \leq 0.05$ indicates no significant difference). The results show that AdaBoost demonstrates a statistically significant difference in recall compared to both LGBM and CatBoost, while exhibiting similar performance to GradientBoost and XGBoost. Furthermore, GradientBoost, XGBoost, and CatBoost show no statistically significant differences in recall when compared with the other algorithms, indicating comparable performance across these methods. Notably, the recall performance of AdaBoost and LGBM differs significantly, further confirming the divergence between these two models.

Table 4: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of estimators vs F1-measure.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -1.260$ $p = 0.463$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.244$ $p = 0.075$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -4.178$ $p = 0.009$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -3.020$ $p = 0.029$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 1.443$ $p = 0.209$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -2.047$ $p = 0.096$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.086$ $p = 0.062$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.324$ $p = 0.243$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 2.244$ $p = 0.075$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.580$ $p = 0.175$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.957$ $p = 0.383$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.103$ $p = 0.922$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 4.178$ $p = 0.009$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 2.219$ $p = 0.077$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.957$ $p = 0.383$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.418$ $p = 0.882$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 3.020$ $p = 0.029$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.295$ $p = 0.252$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.103$ $p = 0.922$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.418$ $p = 0.882$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

Table 4 reports the p-values for pairwise comparisons of the F1-measure across different algorithms, evaluating statistical significance at the 5% level. The results indicate that AdaBoost does not show a statistically significant difference in F1 performance when compared to GradientBoost and XGBoost, but exhibits a significant difference when compared to LGBM and CatBoost. Both GradientBoost and XGBoost demonstrate no significant difference in F1-measure when compared with the other four algorithms, suggesting consistent performance. In contrast, LGBM and CatBoost show statistically significant differences in performance relative to AdaBoost, while exhibiting similar performance to each other, as well as to GradientBoost and XGBoost.

Table 5: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of estimators vs accuracy.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -1.294$ $p = 0.252$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.195$ $p = 0.080$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -4.255$ $p = 0.008$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	t statistic: -3.040 p value: 0.029 $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 1.317$ $p = 0.245$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -1.681$ $p = 0.154$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.913$ $p = 0.114$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.259$ $p = 0.264$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 2.195$ $p = 0.080$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.643$ $p = 0.161$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.908$ $p = 0.405$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.097$ $p = 0.926$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 4.255$ $p = 0.008$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 2.139$ $p = 0.085$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.908$ $p = 0.405$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.841$ $p = 0.439$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 3.040$ $p = 0.029$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.276$ $p = 0.785$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.097$ $p = 0.926$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.841$ $p = 0.439$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

Table 5 presents the p -values obtained from pairwise t -tests to evaluate whether statistically significant performance differences exist between boosting algorithms in terms of accuracy, when the number of estimators is increased. Upon examination, there is no statistically significant difference in accuracy between AdaBoost and both Gradient Boosting and XGBoost, as their corresponding p -values exceed the 0.05 significance threshold. However, statistically significant differences are observed between AdaBoost and both LightGBM and CatBoost, indicating that these models yield notably different accuracy levels under variations in the number of estimators. For Gradient Boosting, no significant performance differences are found when compared with any of the other models namely, AdaBoost, XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost. This suggests that Gradient Boosting exhibits stable performance relative to other algorithms under estimator tuning.

7.2. Statistical Significance Tests for Learning Rate vs Performance Parameters

In this section, we analyze the relationship between learning rate and model performance metrics by evaluating the corresponding t -statistics and p -values. A p -value greater than 0.05 indicates that there is no statistically significant performance difference between two models at the 5% significance level. Conversely, a p -value less than 0.05 suggests that the performance difference is statistically significant.

Table 6: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of learning rate vs precision.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -1.674$ $p = 0.155$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.760$ $p = 0.040$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -4.017$ $p = 0.010$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.886$ $p = 0.034$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 1.674$ $p = 0.155$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.671$ $p = 0.532$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.803$ $p = 0.448$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.433$ $p = 0.211$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 2.760$ $p = 0.040$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.671$ $p = 0.532$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.870$ $p = 0.402$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.362$ $p = 0.732$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 4.017$ $p = 0.010$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.803$ $p = 0.448$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.870$ $p = 0.402$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.439$ $p = 0.679$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 2.886$ $p = 0.034$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.433$ $p = 0.211$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.362$ $p = 0.732$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.439$ $p = 0.679$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

Focusing on accuracy, AdaBoost performs similarly to GradientBoost, but differs significantly from XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost. GradientBoost, XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost exhibit statistically similar accuracy, indicating stable performance across learning rates. For precision, as shown in Table 6, no pairwise comparison shows a significant difference. This suggests all models perform comparably in terms of precision, regardless of the learning rate.

Table 7: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of learning rate vs recall.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -0.642$ $p = 0.549$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.854$ $p = 0.123$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.710$ $p = 0.148$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.098$ $p = 0.322$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 0.642$ $p = 0.549$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -1.190$ $p = 0.258$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.290$ $p = 0.254$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.713$ $p = 0.505$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 1.854$ $p = 0.123$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.190$ $p = 0.258$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.145$ $p = 0.899$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.135$ $p = 0.899$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 1.710$ $p = 0.148$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.290$ $p = 0.254$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.145$ $p = 0.899$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.293$ $p = 0.781$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 1.098$ $p = 0.322$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.883$ $p = 0.418$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.135$ $p = 0.898$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.293$ $p = 0.781$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

Furthermore, as observed in Table 7, variations in the learning rate do not lead to substantial performance differences for most models with respect to recall. However, AdaBoost demonstrates statistically significant differences in recall performance when compared to all four algorithms: GradientBoost, XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost. GradientBoost differs significantly only from AdaBoost, while showing no significant difference in recall performance when compared to XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost. Additionally, XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost exhibit similar recall performance to one another and do not differ significantly, though they all show statistically significant differences when compared with AdaBoost.

Table 8: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of learning rate vs F1-measure.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -4.605$ $p = 0.006$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.809$ $p = 0.038$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -5.232$ $p = 0.003$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -4.523$ $p = 0.006$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 4.605$ $p = 0.006$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.474$ $p = 0.795$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.828$ $p = 0.505$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.404$ $p = 0.703$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 2.809$ $p = 0.038$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.474$ $p = 0.795$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -1.115$ $p = 0.315$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.756$ $p = 0.484$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 5.232$ $p = 0.003$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.828$ $p = 0.505$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.115$ $p = 0.315$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.756$ $p = 0.484$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 4.523$ $p = 0.006$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.404$ $p = 0.703$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.756$ $p = 0.484$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.756$ $p = 0.484$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

Table 8 presents the pairwise statistical comparison of models based on the F1-measure with respect to varying learning rates. The results indicate that AdaBoost exhibits a statistically significant difference in F1 performance when compared to GradientBoost, XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost. In contrast, GradientBoost does not show any statistically significant difference in F1 performance when compared to the other algorithms, indicating stable and comparable behavior across models.

Table 9: Pairwise t -test comparison of ensemble boosting algorithms for number of learning rate vs F1-measure.

Algorithms	AdaBoost	GradientBoost	XGBoost	LGBM	CatBoost
AdaBoost		$t = -2.781$ $p = 0.039$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -2.943$ $p = 0.032$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -4.504$ $p = 0.006$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = -3.209$ $p = 0.024$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis
GradientBoost	$t = 2.444$ $p = 0.058$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.987$ $p = 0.369$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -1.358$ $p = 0.232$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.540$ $p = 0.612$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
XGBoost	$t = 2.943$ $p = 0.032$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.987$ $p = 0.369$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = -0.929$ $p = 0.365$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.421$ $p = 0.691$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
LGBM	$t = 4.504$ $p = 0.006$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.358$ $p = 0.232$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.929$ $p = 0.365$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis		$t = 0.462$ $p = 0.664$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis
CatBoost	$t = 3.209$ $p = 0.024$ $p < 0.05$ we can reject null hypothesis	$t = 1.292$ $p = 0.264$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = 0.421$ $p = 0.691$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	$t = -0.462$ $p = 0.664$ $p > 0.05$ we cannot reject null hypothesis	

As shown in Table 9, XGBoost exhibits a statistically significant difference in performance compared to AdaBoost, while demonstrating similar performance to GradientBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost. Similarly, both LGBM and CatBoost significantly differ from AdaBoost, but show no statistically significant differences when compared to GradientBoost, XGBoost, or each other. These results indicate a consistent pattern of performance among GradientBoost, XGBoost, LGBM, and CatBoost, with AdaBoost being the outlier in terms of accuracy across varying learning rates.

8. Conclusion and Future Direction

In this study, we developed a spam detection model using various boosting algorithms, focusing on the tuning of two key hyperparameters: the number of estimators and the learning rate. We evaluated model performance using standard classification metrics accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-measure and conducted an in-depth analysis of bias and variance errors with respect to these hyperparameters. Our results reveal that AdaBoost and GradientBoost consistently underperform compared to XGBoost, CatBoost, and LGBM, which demonstrate comparable and superior performance in terms of both accuracy and generalization error.

To validate these findings, we performed statistical significance testing between model pairs at the 5% significance level across all four performance metrics. The results confirm that XGBoost, CatBoost, and LGBM form a statistically similar group, outperforming the other two models in most scenarios.

The study demonstrates that ensemble learning techniques are highly effective for the spam detection task, offering high accuracy and reliability. Based on our findings, practitioners can confidently select from among the top-performing boosting algorithms for deployment in real-world applications, such as integration into email service provider servers.

For future work, we plan to explore deep neural network architectures, particularly Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models, which are well-suited for sequential text data. These models offer the advantage of automatic feature extraction, potentially reducing the need for extensive preprocessing while improving detection performance.

References

- [1] I. Fette, N. Sadeh, and A. Tomasic, "Learning to detect phishing emails," in *Proc. 16th Int. Conf. World Wide Web*, Banff, AB, Canada, May 2007, pp. 649–656.
- [2] J. C. Sipiior, B. T. Ward, and P. G. Bonner, "Should spam be on the menu?," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 47, no. 6, pp. 59–63, 2004.
- [3] SecureList, "Spam and phishing in 2021," [Online]. Available: <https://securelist.com/spam-and-phishing-in-2021/105713/>, Accessed: Jun. 27, 2022.

- [4] J. J. Alferes, A. Brogi, J. A. Leite, and L. M. Pereira, “An evolvable rule-based e-mail agent,” in *Proc. Portuguese Conf. Artif. Intell.*, Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, Dec. 2003, pp. 394–408.
- [5] K. Albrecht, N. Burri, and R. Wattenhofer, “Spamato—An extendable spam filter system,” in *Proc. CEAS*, 2005.
- [6] M. R. Islam, M. U. Chowdhury, and W. Zhou, “An innovative spam filtering model based on support vector machine,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Intell. Modelling, Control and Automation (CIMCA) and Intell. Agents, Web Technol. and Internet Commerce (IAWTIC)*, IEEE, 2005, vol. 2, pp. 348–353.
- [7] K. Kandasamy and P. Koroth, “An integrated approach to spam classification on Twitter using URL analysis, natural language processing and machine learning techniques,” in *Proc. IEEE Students’ Conf. Electr., Electron. and Comput. Sci.*, Mar. 2014, pp. 1–5.
- [8] W. A. Awad and S. M. ELseuofi, “Machine learning methods for spam e-mail classification,” *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Inf. Technol.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 173–184, 2011.
- [9] B. Yu and Z. B. Xu, “A comparative study for content-based dynamic spam classification using four machine learning algorithms,” *Knowl.-Based Syst.*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 355–362, 2008.
- [10] K. C. Ying, S. W. Lin, Z. J. Lee, and Y. T. Lin, “An ensemble approach applied to classify spam e-mails,” *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 2197–2201, 2010.
- [11] S. Seth and S. Biswas, “Multimodal spam classification using deep learning techniques,” in *Proc. 13th Int. Conf. Signal-Image Technol. and Internet-Based Syst. (SITIS)*, IEEE, Dec. 2017, pp. 346–349.
- [12] J. Devlin, M. W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, “BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.04805*, 2018.
- [13] Q. Yaseen, “Spam email detection using deep learning techniques,” *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 184, pp. 853–858, 2021.
- [14] H. Yang, Q. Liu, S. Zhou, and Y. Luo, “A spam filtering method based on multimodal fusion,” *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 1152, 2019.
- [15] L. Breiman, “Bagging predictors,” *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 24, pp. 123–140, 1996.
- [16] Y. Freund and R. E. Schapire, “A decision-theoretic generalization of on-line learning and an application to boosting,” *J. Comput. Syst. Sci.*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 119–139, 1997.
- [17] J. Friedman, “Greedy Function Approximation: A Gradient Boosting Machine,” [Online]. Available: <http://www.salford-systems.com/doc.GreedyFuncApproxSS>, 1999.
- [18] PostNetwork, “Linear Regression using Gradient Descent,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.postnetwork.co/linear-regression-using-gradient-decent/>, Accessed: Jul. 10, 2022.
- [19] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, “XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system,” in *Proc. 22nd ACM SIGKDD Int. Conf. Knowl. Discov. Data Min.*, Aug. 2016, pp. 785–794.

- [20] G. Ke et al., “LightGBM: A highly efficient gradient boosting decision tree,” in *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [21] A. V. Dorogush, V. Ershov, and A. Gulin, “CatBoost: Gradient boosting with categorical features support,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.11363*, 2018.
- [22] UCI Repository, “Spambase Data Set,” [Online]. Available: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/spambase>, Accessed: Jul. 23, 2022.
- [23] Scikit-learn, “Precision-Recall,” [Online]. Available: https://scikit-learn.org/stable/auto_examples/model_selection/plot_precision_recall.html, Accessed: Jul. 23, 2022.
- [24] B. J. Erickson and F. Kitamura, “Magician’s corner: 9. Performance metrics for machine learning models,” *Radiol. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 3, no. 3, e200126, 2021.
- [25] F. Pedregosa et al., “Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python,” *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 12, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
- [26] S. Raschka, “MLxtend: Providing machine learning and data science utilities and extensions to Python’s scientific computing stack,” *J. Open Source Softw.*, vol. 3, no. 24, p. 638, 2018.
- [27] S. Raschka, “Bias-variance decomposition for classification and regression losses,” [Online]. Available: http://rasbt.github.io/mlxtend/user_guide/evaluate/bias_variance_decomp/.
- [28] T. G. Dietterich, “Approximate statistical tests for comparing supervised classification learning algorithms,” *Neural Comput.*, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 1895–1923, 1998.
- [29] E. Häglund, “Estimating Prediction Intervals with Machine Learning and Monte Carlo Methods in Online Advertising,” M.Sc. Thesis, 2020.
- [30] R. R. Bouckaert and E. Frank, “Evaluating the replicability of significance tests for comparing learning algorithms,” in *Proc. Pacific-Asia Conf. Knowl. Discov. Data Min.*, Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2004, pp. 3–12.